

IMPROVEMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS OF
ECONOMIC GROWTH IN THE SERVICE FIELD

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7548527>

ELSEVIER

Abstract. The organization of the organizational and economic mechanism that has been formed in the service sector in our republic for full control and management of the services market. Classification of indicators that determine economic efficiency in the service sector, and the study of the methodology for assessing labor efficiency.

Keywords: Service, market economy, labor efficiency, tax incentives, business entities, information and communication services, financial services, transportation services, real estate services, education services, healthcare services, rental and leasing, production activities.

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Received: 17-01-2023

Accepted: 18-01-2023

Published: 22-01-2023

Abstract. Организация организационно-экономического механизма, сформировавшегося в сфере услуг в нашей республике для полного контроля и управления деятельностью рынка услуг. Классификация показателей, определяющих экономическую эффективность в сфере услуг, и исследование методологии оценки эффективности труда.

Keywords: Сервис, рыночная экономика, эффективность труда, налоговые льготы, хозяйствующие субъекты, услуги в сфере информации и связи, финансовые услуги, транспортные услуги, услуги связанные с недвижимым имуществом, услуги в сфере образования, услуги в сфере здравоохранения, услуги в области аренды и лизинга, производственной деятельности..

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Abstract. Республикада хизмат кўрсатиш соҳасида шаклланган ташкилий-иқтисодий механизм хизматлар бозорида фаолиятини тўлақонли назорат қилиш ва бошқаришни ташкил этиш. Сервис иқтисодиётида иқтисодий самарадорликни белгиловчи кўрсаткичлар таснифлаш ҳамда меҳнат самарадорлигини баҳолаш услубияти тадқиқ этиш..

Keywords: Сервис, бозор иқтисодиёти, меҳнат самарадорлиги, солиқ имтиёзлари, иқтисодий субъектлар, аҳборот ва алоқа соҳасидаги хизматлар, молия хизматлари, транспорт хизматлари, кучмас мулк билан боғлиқ хизматлар, таълим соҳасидаги хизматлар, соғлиқни сақлаш соҳасидаги хизматлар, ижара ва лизинг бўйича хизматлар, индустриал фаолият.

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Enter.

In the development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to use a systematic approach to the study of economic systems and ratios, a comprehensive assessment, a comparative and comparative analysis, a statistical and dynamic approach, and grouping methods to improve the organizational and economic mechanism of the development of the service sector.

Today, the organizational and economic mechanism formed in the service sector in our republic does not have the ability to organize full control and

management of their activities in the service market. Therefore, it is important to optimize the organizational structure of the service sector.

In the context of the development of market relations, the structural structure of service industries is a complex organizational and economic structure.

According to its nature and content, the service sector includes various forms and directions of human activity, which are related to the creation of conditions for the development of human capital, which are related to ensuring the quality of modern life, and ensuring the transition of the division of labor to a relatively high level. The main focus is on the development of modern networks with a large capacity of science and information technology in the use of intellectual resources.

Such a situation in the development of society requires a wider development of the service sector compared to other sectors of the economy. The development of the service sector and industries has an impact on the changes in the composition of the gross domestic product of the countries based on the developed market economy.

Currently, the contribution of the service sector in the structure of the gross domestic product, which is created to include a certain country among the developed countries, is higher than 65 percent.

At the current stage of the development of the economy of our country, the requirements for the number and quality of services are increasing. This makes it necessary to determine the factors of economic growth and achieve economic efficiency in service industries. From this point of view, in paragraph 3.2 of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, "rapid development of the service sector, increasing the role and share of services in the formation of the gross domestic product, the composition of the provided services, first of all, at the expense of their modern high-tech types the task of "change". Based on the effective solution of these tasks, it is important to improve the efficiency of service sector entities and improve the quality of services provided to the population.

Analysis of literature on the topic.

In the scientific literature, the nature, content, methods of calculating labor efficiency and productivity in the service economy, development of the service sector and improvement of the quality of services provided to the population, evaluation of the efficiency of economic entities, some aspects of the change of the qualitative conditions that constitute efficiency are scientifically, theoretically and methodologically researched.

Academician K.Kh.Abdurahmanov in his textbook Labor economy: theory and practice [2, 426-446 p.] the essence, content, formation of labor resources,

interdependence of labor resources and human resources, labor efficiency and its factors, factors of increasing labor productivity and tools, the concepts of the highest labor productivity, the concept of decent work of the International Labor Organization (ILO), the problems of mobility of labor resources are highlighted.

The study guide written under the editorship of M.Q.Pardaev examines the problems of development of the service, service and tourism sectors, the formation of labor resources in the service sector and the effectiveness of their use, the factors and directions of increasing labor productivity in the sector.

Also, the social, economic and institutional foundations of the development of the service and tourism sectors have been scientifically researched.

In this article, the qualitative and quantitative assessment of the factors of economic growth in the service industry based on the previous researches, and the determination of the contribution of each of these factors to the growth of the service sector and industry are considered important scientific issues even today.

T.D. Burmenko's work "Экономика сферы услуг (Вводный курс)" there are ways of formation and use of labor resources in enterprises, factors and reserves of increasing labor productivity and efficiency and methods of their measurement, factors of increasing efficiency of use of labor resources in enterprises, socio-economic nature of wages, work The form and methods of payment of the fee, its main task and functions have been researched.

Management and organization and sphere of management: theory and practice: Service management and operation - 2nd international edition. (per.s engl nar. nauk ryad. V.V. Kulibanovoy) / K. Khaksiver, B. Render, R. S. Russell, R. G. Murdik - Spbi. dr: peter bux. 2002. - S. 496. In this work, the formation and development of the service economy, the system of scientific organization and management of labor in the service sector, its methods and tools, the service "Economy and innovative technologies" scientific electronic journal. No. 2, March-April, 2017 No. 2, 2017 www.iqtisodiyot.uz 3 factors and reserves of increasing labor productivity and efficiency in demonstration enterprises and methods of their measurement, factors of increasing the efficiency of the use of labor resources in enterprises, socio-economic nature of wages, work Forms and methods of payment of fees, its main tasks and functions are researched.

In his work, Russian scientist A.A. Tkachenko researched the directions of expanding jobs in the service sector and effective use of labor resources, creating new jobs in the sector, giving tax incentives to employers who create jobs, and increasing labor efficiency.

In her work, Russian scientist A.P. Erofeeva researched the development and implementation of the personnel management system in service enterprises, the foreign experience of the personnel management system in the field, methods of

researching the personnel management system, and the processes of modernization of the personnel management system in service enterprises.

In the works of the above-mentioned authors, the general aspects of economic growth are determined based on the assessment of the impact of various factors on economic efficiency. In these studies, the impact of intensive and extensive factors on economic growth was not evaluated.

Accordingly, the scientific essence of our research is that the general index of the dynamics of economic growth in service industries and sectors was studied based on the classification of intensive and extensive factors.

Research methodology.

During the research, the dialectical and systematic approach to the study of economic systems and ratios, comprehensive assessment, comparative and comparative analysis, statistical and dynamic approach, and grouping methods were used to ensure economic growth and evaluate efficiency in service industries.

Economic efficiency reflects the results of the activities of economic operators, and social efficiency reflects the social efficiency of economic entities and its impact on various aspects of society.

In this case, social and economic efficiency were found to be interrelated to a certain extent. Also, the indicators determining the economic efficiency in the service economy were classified and the method of labor efficiency assessment was researched.

Analysis and results.

In the present era, when new information technologies are widely distributed, the development of the world community has reached such a stage that this situation is affecting and changing all aspects of social and economic life.

Economists recognize such changes in socio-economic life as the fact that the development of human civilization has entered a new stage.

According to them, knowledge and skills of people and information are the decisive factor at this stage of civilization. The development trend of modern society is mainly characterized by the transition from a raw and industrial economy to a service economy.

In this, the main focus is on the development of modern networks with a large capacity of science and information technology in the use of intellectual resources.

Such a situation in the development of society requires a wider development of the service sector compared to other sectors of the economy. Today, the socio-economic development of the countries of the world differs sharply in terms of its meaning and content from the previous stages.

A new interpretation of economic growth requires modern, conceptual approaches in world economics. In particular, effective activity in the service economy is somewhat wider than industrial activity.

In our republic, structural changes are taking place in the service sector, as well as in all types of economic activity. In particular, when analyzing statistical data from 2016 to 2021, the largest share of total services in 2016 was healthcare services.

(22.2%), this indicator decreased during 2017-2020 and reached 28.5% in 2021, or the share of health services in total services decreased by 6.3% during 2017-2020 .

Also, it was found that during the analyzed years 2016-2021, in the structure of total services, motor transport (1.7%) and trade services (1.7%) have a tendency to decrease.

In 2016, the share of accommodation and food services in the total services was 21.1%, while in 2021 this indicator was 32.3% and increased by 11.2%.

In addition, during the analyzed period, in the service sector, information and communication services (11.8%), financial services (8.2%), transport services (7.9%), real estate services (5.6%)), education services (23.0%), health services (6.3%), rental and leasing services (1.1%), computers, personal items and household goods repair services (7.3 %), personal services (0.6%), services in architecture, engineering research, technical testing and analysis (2.6%) increased.

The volume of services provided by the main types of economic activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan
(in billion soums)

Indicators	2016		2017		2018		2019		2020		2021	
	Size	%	Size	%	Size	%	Size	%	Size	%	Size	%
Services - total	97050,0	14,7	18811,0	10,7	50889,8	108,9	93697,8	13,2	19978,5	30,0	84165,4	19,5
services in the field of information and communication	6306,8	114,6	8196,7	21,3	10332,6	15,9	10891,7	08,3	3852,3	23,8	7755,1	26,4

personal items and household items repair	2187,8	15,6	2329,2	102,6	2630,7	104,2	200,1	107,1	3347,8	94,5	4680,5	122,9
rental and leasing services	2270,1	117,6	2589,2	102,1	3297,4	110,4	3733,5	98,3	4149,0	98,4	5351,0	118,7
services in the field of health	1416,3	122,2	1701,5	116,9	2220,0	113,4	3104,3	114,7	3386,7	94,8	5105,9	128,5
service in the field of education	3263,0	107,8	4402,0	125,6	5416,5	110,5	7164,9	109,5	8539,4	101,0	12021,8	130,8
related to real estate services	405,1	117,5	4026,5	106,6	4949,2	107,9	5950,7	104,7	6016,9	90,0	8081,1	123,1
trade services	7368,2	120,5	32006,9	100,3	39743,4	104,9	48748,2	107,4	57572,7	103,8	72483,3	112,3
living and dining services	3038,7	121,1	3649,6	12,1	4673,3	107,0	5933,6	107,3	5431,7	80,3	8375,4	132,3
including: auto transport services	19216,7	117,2	20232,9	102,1	21786,8	101,6	25527,5	105,1	28474,1	101,4	36249,3	115,5
transport services	0617,8	107,8	36217,2	109,9	44159,4	104,5	54473,5	106,7	53662,9	91,4	67238,6	115,7
financial services	9898,4	119,8	15023,8	36,5	1296,3	21,5	4036,6	47,0	5783,0	25,6	9733,3	28,0

personal services	2915,5	113,8	3134,4	00,7	3700,6	102,2	575,6	105,4	5032,2	94,7	6764,1	114,4
architecture, engineering research, technical	1132,6	115,3	1611,7	124,7	2953,6	118,1	543,1	115,5	4907,5	93,3	6306,8	117,9
other services	3229,7	114,9	3922,3	111,8	5516,8	121,2	7342,0	116,3	8296,4	9,7	10268,5	113,0

Source: calculated based on the information of the State Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

* Formed according to the main types of services specified in the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 1754 of May 10, 2012.

Another organizational mechanism for increasing the efficiency of service enterprises is an information system that serves the industry. This system includes, in our opinion, the following: advertising agencies, marketing service centers, permanent or traveling exhibitions, media and electronic communication systems, etc. In our opinion, the further development of information supply in the service sector will provide an opportunity to justify the perspective of the population's ability to pay for services, to assess the dynamics of the growth of this sector, and to improve the quality and efficiency of the services provided. For this purpose, it is necessary to establish a special service for researching the demand for services and marketing centers at the regional level. This organizational structure includes the following areas of activity:

- development of scientific and practical manuals for studying demand and supply for new types of services;
- preparation of reports, booklets, reports on the service conjuncture at the regional level for subjects who feel the need for services;
- conducting questionnaires, sociological research to determine the quality of the provided service;
- participation in social events, fairs, exhibitions to solve problems in the field of services.

An important organizational link that provides information provision of service enterprises is advertising activity. Its importance for this industry is the dissemination of information about services to the public in various forms, while advertising is not only a source of information, but it is an important organizational

mechanism that stimulates new needs for services and the ability of the population to pay.

Summary.

The economic growth of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be defined as the growth of real GDP or the growth of real GDP per capita. This ensures an increase in the volume of production used to solve domestic and international socio-economic problems. Economic growth is measured by the growth rate of GDP. Economic growth is characterized by an increase in the volume of production due to the attraction of additional resources to economic circulation and their quality improvement.

Economic growth, which is achieved by increasing the quantity of resources of the same quality, has an extensive nature and is ensured only by improving the quality of resources. At the same time, it is considered to have an intensive character.

Economic growth is determined by factors: natural resources, labor resources, capital, technology and production organization. Economic growth is also influenced by indirect factors such as the level of market monopolization, the tax situation in the country, prices for production resources, the development of the credit-banking system, and investments.

The problems of efficiency and quality of economic growth are of particular importance for Russia. The Russian economy is characterized by the low competitiveness of local products, excessive emphasis on energy and raw material extraction, poor development of imports of finished goods, low labor productivity, poor financing of foreign investors, short service life of machines, etc. Due to these reasons, the rate of economic growth and productivity of our country is very low.

The development prospects of the local economy and its competitiveness in the world market will depend to a decisive extent on the possibility of moving to a new path of economic development that will improve the quality and speed of economic growth in Russia.

Organizational provision of employees' activities in service enterprises remains a primary task in terms of their effective management. Also, the demand for managers and specialists who have mastered the methods of achieving high quality and increasing labor productivity in the process of service delivery is increasing.

The general labor results of the company's employees depend on the personal labor results of each employee. Therefore, it is necessary to maintain a certain order for them to work together, start and finish work, and observe breaks. A clear mechanism for maintaining labor discipline is also necessary. Currently, the role of information in the services market is growing seriously.

The high need for information and the rapid development of information processes in order to increase the efficiency of service delivery bring to the fore the creation of its organizational departments in enterprises. In fact, the demand for such information systems services will expand to cover the regional services market.

In our opinion, information departments in enterprises should include the following components:

- collecting initial information about the demand and supply of services in the services market;
- development of data processing software;
- creation of a database based on the existing collected and collected information.

The effect of improving the collection, processing and delivery of information on service delivery is manifested in reducing transaction costs, increasing the efficiency of service provision, improving material and technical support, and accelerating the circulation of financial resources.

Therefore, in our opinion, it is important to create a database of information resources about service industry networks, to organize their basic set, and it is a source for researching the directions of perspective development of the industry.

In our opinion, it is necessary to form an information supply on the implementation of the state program for the development of the service sector at the regional level. Accordingly, the data bank plays an important role in the implementation of the following activities for service entities operating in the region:

- allows residents of the region, enterprises, entrepreneurs to get complete information about their services through the data bank;
- creates an opportunity to use information for the entire population by opening and placing information points at the regional level.

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